

DIYbioX Protocol: Extracting DNA from Soil and Sediments

Extracting and sequencing DNA from soils and sediments can give insight into ecosystems from the past. Large volumes of sediment need to be used in order to maximize the chances of recovering sedimentary DNA (sedaDNA).

Reagents needed:

1. 100-mL, 1-mL, and 10-mL pipettes and tips. 2. 1.5-mL tubes (at least one per extract, depending upon final volume eluted).
3. 50-mL tubes (one per sample).
4. Rotary mixer, wheel, or similar device to keep samples constantly in motion during incubation steps, capable of holding 50-mL tubes.
5. Oven large enough to accommodate the rotary mixer. 6. Centrifuge capable of holding 50-mL tubes and reaching a force of $2,500\times g$. 7. Vortex-Genie[®] Vortex and a Vortex Adapter capable of shaking two 50-mL tubes simultaneously (CamBio).
8. Garnet grit: aliquots provided in the PowerMax[®] Bead Tubes from the PowerMax[™] DNA Isolation Kit.
9. Bulat (9) extraction buffer: 0.02 g/mL Sarcosyl, 50 mM Tris- HCl (pH 8.0), 20 mM NaCl, 3.5% 2-mercaptoethanol, 50 mM 1,4-Dithio-L-threitol (DTT), 2 mM *N*-phenacylthiazone bromide (PTB), 0.8 g/mL Proteinase K (see Note 1).
10. Solutions C1–C6 from the PowerMaxSoil[™] DNA Isolation Kit (Cambio).
11. HPLC grade water.

Protocol:

1. Add 10 g wet weight of sediment to a 50-mL tube containing garnet grits.
2. Add 12 mL of Bulat extraction buffer or 15 mL of PowerMax[®] Bead Solution C2 (containing guanidine thiocyanate) (see Note 2).
3. Add 1.2 mL of C1 solution (sodium dodecyl sulfate solution) (see Note 3).
4. Vortex for 10 min at the highest speed to ensure cell lysis and/ or release of DNA from soil particles.
5. If using Bulat buffer, incubate overnight with rotation in an oven set to 65°C. If

using PowerMax[®] Bead Solution, proceed to step 6.

6. Spin the 50-mL tube at 2,500×*g* for 3 min and transfer the supernatant to a clean tube containing 5 mL of C3 (see Note 4).
7. Incubate at 4°C for 10 min to aid precipitation of non-DNA organic and inorganic materials, humic substances, cell debris, and proteins (see Note 5).
8. Spin the tube in the centrifuge at 2,500×*g* for 4 min, then transfer the supernatant to a clean tube containing 4 mL C3 solution.
9. Incubate at 4°C for 10 min.
10. Spin at 2,500×*g* for 4 min, then remove the supernatant to a clean 50-mL tube and add 30 mL of solution C4 (guanidine HCl—*isopropanol* solution).
11. Spin the resulting solution through silicon spin filters (see Note 6).
12. Add 10 mL of solution C5, an ethanol-based wash solution, to clean the DNA that is bound to the silica filter membrane in the spin filter (see Note 7).
13. Add 1.5–5 mL of solution C6 (Tris buffer solution) to the spin filter membrane and centrifuge at 2500 × *g* in order to elute the bound DNA (see Note 8).
14. Transfer the elution to 1.5-mL tube(s).
15. Store the DNA extract at –20°C.